

TECHNOLOGY FACILITATED GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

A TOOLKIT FOR CHANGE

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Technology Facilitated Gender Based Violence: A Toolkit for Change

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Acknowledgements

We are incredibly grateful for the expertise, knowledge, and insights shared by our workshop collaborators: Eva Blum-Dumontet, Head of Movement Building and Policy at Chayn; Emma Kay, Founder of WalkSafe; Georgia Street, Helpline Practitioner, Revenge Porn Helpline, South West Grid for Learning; Tallulah Belassie-Page, Senior Policy and Campaigns Officer, Suzy Lamplugh Trust; Jodi Leedham, Service Manager for the Technology-Facilitated Abuse and Economic Empowerment Team, Refuge; Melanie Fullbrook, representation for Women in Data; Ailish McEntee, Safeguarding Nurse at MSI Reproductive; Daphne Metland, Director at Thrive Agency. We would also like to thank Rebecca Hitchen, Head of Policy and Campaigns at End Violence Against Women Coalition (EVAW) for additional feedback. The toolkit was skilfully designed and built by Scott Davis at Twenty3Creative. This project has been supported by the ESRC Impact Accelerator Account at Coventry University, without which none of this would have been possible.

Abstract

This report presents a walkthrough of a toolkit that has been built to increase awareness and knowledge of support, advice, and information on technology-facilitated gender-based violence (TFGBV) for a range of audiences. In what follows, we give an account of three workshops held with expert collaborators, from sectors including advocacy, support services, healthcare, and the tech-industry and/or representatives of women in the tech industry. The project has made use of co-creation and co-production methods to identify significant gaps and challenges for these sectors in tackling TFGBV. Co-creation was chosen for the way it empowers stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle, draws on diverse experiences and expertise, and encourages stakeholder buy-in and pathways to impact and implementation. The outcome has been the development and design of a toolkit that collates already existing materials and resources into one resource library, and that allows users to select filters to narrow down the information that is most relevant to them. The toolkit thus has potential benefits to victim-survivors of TFGBV, but can also be used by friends and family, within health and legal settings and sectors, and by students and researchers or members of the public with a vested interest in learning more. The following report guides the reader through each section of the website that we have built, demonstrating its functions and affordances, while identifying possible future developments for such a valuable tool for change, and its necessity in the context of an endemic of violence against women and girls.

Background

Technology-facilitated gender-based violence (TFGBV) is a broad term used to delineate the embeddedness of technology in forms of abuse, violence, harassment, and intimidation. It is gender-based violence (GBV) in that it is used to harm women^a. In this report, we follow the United Nations definition of TFGBV as being “any act that is committed, assisted, aggravated, or amplified by the use of information communication technologies or other digital tools, that results in or is likely to result in physical, sexual, psychological, social, political, or economic harm, or other infringements of rights and freedoms” (UN Women, 2022). Thus, while it is sometimes used synonymously with online gender-based violence (OGBV), we take it to include the full range of technologies and forms of violence are captured by the term.

TFGBV can include targeted harassment through social media (e.g. trolling, pile-ons) (Lumsden & Morgan, 2018; Ortiz, 2020). It can take the form of intimate partner violence, for example through tracking and surveilling a persons’ location through GPS, Bluetooth, and various mobile phone apps (Woodlock, 2017); or using devices like camera-enabled doorbells and home security cameras (Slupska & Tanczer, 2021). It is also used to define forms of image based abuse (IBA), for example, through mobile phone technology that allows people to send photos of genitals without the receivers’ consent (Ringrose et al, 2021; McGlynn & Rackley, 2017); or where images are used to threaten, intimidate, or humiliate a person by sharing personal information (e.g. doxxing) (Douglas, 2016). It can also include images, video, and text generated through AI technology that attempt to impersonate a victim-survivor (Chowdhury & Lakshmi, 2023). TFGBV is constantly evolving in response to new technologies, including developing forms of abuse that incorporates emerging AI and generative AI and immersive technology. It can include both sexual violence and non-sexual violence; abusers can be known to the victim-survivor, but equally can be unknown; and there might be differing levels of digital, online, and technologically enabled abuse in relation to physical or ‘real life’ abuse - and indeed, TFGBV blurs the dividing line between ‘digital’ and ‘non-digital’ abuse.

^a We use the term ‘women’ in this report to mean any person who identifies as a woman. However, we also recognise that the forms of TFGBV experienced by cis-women and trans-women can be different, and transphobic TFGBV is often used to compound the marginalisation of trans-women in society. Often, TFGBV is discussed in relation to ‘women and girls’, however, our focus in this report is largely on adult women.

The usefulness of thinking of these different forms of abuse together through the acronym TFGBV is that it captures the complexity of our technologically-driven worlds, and how such technology is often used in ways that reinforce the unequal position of women in our society. Such inequalities are often compounded by the way the effects of TFGBV and OGBV might be disproportionately felt and amplified for minoritised women or those with less privilege - for example, through sexuality, race, class, religion, disability, and other intersections (Dunn, 2020; Glitch, 2023). Women who are already in an abusive relationship are particularly vulnerable to TFGBV (.ibid). TFGBV is also rarely experienced in only one form; for instance, those navigating intimate partner violence are often subject to various forms of technological and physical abuse, financial coercion, and control. Likewise, forms of image-based abuse such as revenge porn or extortion might also be accompanied by cyberstalking or surveillance.

Many practitioners, researchers, and experts agree that TFGBV is increasingly global and pervasive (Glitch & EVAW, 2020), even while many of the highest figures still likely underestimate the true prevalence given that TFGBV is likely to be massively underreported (The Global Partnership, 2023); challenging to track given perpetrators uses of pseudonyms, anonymity, and IP-blockers; and in some cases may be difficult to know when it is happening. For example, if someone is being surveilled by home cameras, or their phone's GPS has been shared with another device without their knowledge, there may be limited evidence that they are being stalked. Such prevalence creates a significant challenge to women's human rights, equal participation in society, and the ability to live a life free from fear or threat. UN Women (2022) identify that violence against women and girls (VAWG) happening online can be as harmful as offline VAWG, "with serious impacts on health and wellbeing as well as serious economic, social and political impacts". We agree, and would include the broader landscape of TFGBV as having adverse effects on people's safety and risk of harm, perpetuated by a continuing underlying culture of sexism and misogyny (Balfour et al, 2023).

In response, a number of groups and organisations - including those in advocacy, support services, research, and activist organisations - have produced material online to help inform people about forms of TFGBV. For example, Refuge have created the Digital Breakup tool. This tool provides information on how technology can facilitate abuse perpetrated by partners and ex-partners in different realms life, including how to keep safe in relation to takeaway food, travel, gaming, and location. Revenge Porn Helpline provide a range of advice on their website concerning IBA covering sextortion, deepfakes, upskirting, among others.

Glitch provides education and training to challenge online abuse targeting Black women, for example on how to be an online active bystander, and how to challenge racism and sexism online in the run up to the UK 2024 General Election. This list is not exhaustive. Indeed, the toolkit that we have created as the outcome of this project, and that we outline in this report, draws together 60 resources produced by a range of organisations, including from the tech industry itself. What this project has aimed to do is fill a gap; this gap being a platform that brings together these excellent resources, and furthermore, one that allows people to filter such information to find the right advice, guidance, information, or support for them. This project's aim has thus been to create a prototype for such a platform.

Method

The research in this report was carried out in collaboration with a number of organisations, including representatives from: Chayn, WalkSafe, Revenge Porn Helpline, Suzy Lamplugh Trust, Refuge, Women in Data, MSI Reproductive, Thrive Agency, and feedback and discussion with the End Violence Against Women Coalition (EVAW), and others.

Our remit for participation was that there was adequate cross-sector contribution to the workshops, based on our previous work that found issues of TFGBV needed multiple perspectives, knowledge, and skills (Balfour et al. 2023). Thus, representatives in our partnerships includes support services (Revenge Porn Helpline, Refuge, Chayn), advocacy groups (EVAW, Suzy Lamplugh Trust), technology industry and representatives of women in this industry (WalkSafe, Women in Data), and health organisations (MSI Reproductive, Thrive Agency). Our approach to the research was through co-production and co-creation methods (see Balfour, et al. (2023) for a discussion on the ethical and relationship-building values embedded in these methods). Our workshop collaborators in this project are experts in their respective fields, and our reasons for bringing them together was done so with the intention that they guide the final output of the project. Thus, three workshops were hosted and designed by us, but led by concerns, challenges, and priorities that were relevant to our collaborators.

All workshop collaborators were provided with a Participant Information Leaflet, and signed a Consent Form. All workshops took place at Coventry University London Campus, between November 2023 and February 2024. The project received ethical approval from Coventry University (P162721).

Workshop 1

The primary aim of workshop 1 was to assess the current state of play in relation to resources available for TFGBV. Our guiding questions for the discussion were:

- How do you view current challenges or policy around tech-facilitated GBV within the context of your own work?
- What concerns do you have or what is missing?

- What do you see as the connection or relationship between all these forms of TBGBV? Can they be addressed together or should they be treated separately?
- Based on your experience, what are the consequences of lacking digital literacy and its relationship to GBV? What forms of literacy are needed?
- What are the key challenge areas or concerns to prioritise? Why are these the most significant? What has been done before to try to address them? What needs to be done now? What are the roadblocks? What kinds of tools and resources are needed (generally and specific to your organisation)?

Out of this workshop came feedback that the participants were interesting moving beyond policy debates, because things in this area of change seemed to move slowly and were less responsive to the demands of a highly adaptable, changing, and fast-moving digital landscape. For the people present, it was felt that policy often lead to grey areas, and legislation often created confusion. TFGBV is complicated and difficult to legislate; for example, workshop collaborators reflected on how law, policy, and legislation conceptualise abuse in relation to deepfakes, when the victim-survivor might have to 'prove' that it is themselves that is the target of abuse when their body might not feature in the image.

Another complication was in terms of the new technology that was being harnessed in TFGBV. Workshop collaborators mentioned the emergence of new AI harms, the 'Internet of Things' (i.e. wearable technology), and the spread of misinformation. It was noted that how technology is built can facilitate and encouraged forms of abuse - for example, in how the infrastructures of social media (e.g. notifications, scrolling) often enable obsessive and fixated behaviours.

Based on these challenges, the workshop collaborators felt the best intervention was an education piece, which also had the potential to be used across the sector. It was felt that a lot of excellent resources already existed, but the missing piece was that there was not a core toolkit or resource that drew them all together. While many organisations had developed useful resources, they were often focused on singular topics based on that organisations' area of expertise (i.e. stalking, or economic abuse) and thus could not capture the overlapping forms of abuse that TFGBV represents. Creating one centralised resource library could prove instrumental for practitioners seeking advice on which service to direct people to; but it could also be helpful for those with a knowledge that abuse was happening to themselves or someone they knew, but didn't know where support or information could

be gained, or even the right terminology. For example, terms like ‘love bombing’ are quite new in the terminology surrounding TFGBV, while others like IBA have several terms used to describe different forms of abuse, such as revenge porn, dick pics, and deepfakes. It was also felt that a third audience might be students, researchers, and the general public, who might be broadly interested in understanding TFGBV given its heightened visibility in public discourse. It was agreed that a toolkit that collated materials already available in the sector into one space could be incredibly valuable.

Workshop 2

The aim of the second workshop was to discuss and agree what should/could be included in such a toolkit. Our workshop collaborators were presented with sheets of paper with the following themes:

- What forms of TFGBV should be covered?
- What forms of tech/platforms should be included?
- Who is potential audience?
- What are the challenges/roadblocks?

Collaborators were then invited to add content and relevant material to these themes (see fig.1). At the end of this activity, we invited people to walk around the room a second time to read the contributions of others. A general discussion of the toolkit preceded this activity. This discussion included reflection on each of the themes. It was noted how difficult such a toolkit would be to produce, since it would be hard to account for all potential users. One example given was where TFGBV was perpetrated when the abuser was in prison, where no one resource speaks directly to this potential audience; another concern was issues with digital access and the digital divide. However, as one person said, “the centre of the onion is also often the broadest”, to express the fact that the core problem can be tackled by addressing the widest set of issues.

Upon completion of the workshop, we wrote down all the contributions, and included the category ‘resources’. Under each category, we then started documenting all resources that we knew of that currently exist and that address the tech/platform, forms of TFGBV, and audience. This document was shared with workshop collaborators for them to add additional resources, if they knew of any we had missed.

- Are there any key words or term missing in the search function? Are there missing resources?
- What needs to be included in any bits of text featured on the tool?
- What could be the future applications? Where would you see such a tool being useful?

This discussion focused the potential users of the toolkit, as well as generated discussion on further features that could ensure user safety. One significant outcome of this workshop was the need to guide users to emergency services as a priority of the toolkit; another was the need to signal that the toolkit itself was not a service in and of itself, but a filter and directory. Potential future applications of the toolkit were discussed and included its downline usefulness to the NHS, City Councils, and the Police.

Following the final feedback workshop, collaborators were emailed versions of the toolkit to provide further suggestions over email or video call. Still in beta-mode, the website was password protected to ensure no public access. All suggestions were acted on to the best of our ability and where funding and time allowed. There are suggestions we have not been able to act upon immediately, and these are discussed below in the walkthrough of the toolkit as issues that may need addressing in any further development.

The Toolkit

The information provided below presents a walkthrough of the TFGBV toolkit generated from the project's workshops, and its functions and affordances. This toolkit remains a pilot site; it is not currently accessible to the public, and is password protected. Any live hosting of the site would need additional funding, as well as requiring careful security checks and regular updating and monitoring to ensure the information and services provided are safe, links are not broken, and information has (not) been updated or changed. As a prototype, all elements of the site could be developed, and as part of the project we gained further feedback from the workshop collaborators on further suggestions and alterations that might be needed.

The landing page

The top of the landing page includes two banners that direct a user to, 1) on the left, contact details for services to contact in an emergency and b) on the right, a resource library of information, services, advice and support (fig.2). As much as possible, and given feedback from workshop collaborators, users have been signposted to emergency services. This is because the toolkit has not been designed to be a support service itself. Although the site is designed to have a broad audience (e.g. healthcare practitioners, service providers, researchers, friends and family etc.), we wanted to ensure those needing immediate help were prioritised. Thus, "I need help now!" appears on the left of the landing page, before any further information about the site, and again on the top right - with a hyperlink that allows people to call the emergency services directly from the toolkit.

This safety feature is located in the banner, so that it is accessible wherever a user is on the site. Also appearing on the landing page is a brief piece of text that includes information on how the toolkit works.

Scrolling down to the bottom of the page (fig.3), the users is able to see definitions of forms of abuse, often experienced in domestic abuse but here written in a broad way and with links to how technology might be implicated in these forms of GBV. Each definition highlights not only what it means, but the kinds of support available. In email correspondence with our workshop collaborators, one participant suggested that these were potentially triggering, and

more autonomy could be given by allowing a click-through to the definitions, meaning the user could choose whether to see definitions of these terms or not. Currently, the logos suggest a click through, meaning this could be added. Alternatively, this element of the landing page could be deleted altogether.

Figure 2 Top of landing page

Figure 3 Bottom of landing page

Like the link to the emergency number, other features are retained in the banner across the toolkit, and remain accessible and fixed to the page regardless of how far a user has scrolled. Across the site is a navigation banner, with click-throughs to Resources, About and Feedback. The search function, top left, takes the user to results based on tags in the resource library. The logo, also top left, returns the user back to the landing page from anywhere within the toolkit.

The final feature that is accessible and carried across the whole of the site is the Quick Exit button. This tool immediately redirects the browser to Google, and removes all data from the search bar/URL box, so that the website does autofill or remember previous search terms (i.e. “cookies”). Currently, from Google, it is possible to return to the toolkit by pressing back, although this could be changed with further development.

I need help now!

This page of the site (fig.4) is dedicated to services that can offer front-line support for people in a crisis or when needing professional help.

The screenshot shows the 'I need help now!' page with the following content:

- Galop:** 0800 999 5428, email [here](#), or chat (bottom right corner of website, <https://galop.org.uk>). Support for LGBT+ victims of abuse and violence. Email and chat available 24 hours a day. Helpline open: Monday - Thursday, 10am to 4:30pm; Friday, 10am to 4:00pm.
- Refuge:** 0808 2000 247 or online [here](#). Support if you are a victim of domestic abuse. The helpline is open 24 hours a day. The chat support is available Monday - Friday 3pm - 10pm. (BSL available)
- Strut Safe:** 0333 335 0026. If you are walking alone and feel unsafe, someone is here on the phone until you reach your destination. Strut Safe is available: Fridays & Saturdays: 7pm - 3am; Sundays: 7pm - 1am.
- National Fraud and Cyber Crime Reporting Centre:** 0300 123 2040 or through the online reporting tool [here](#). Reporting illegal behaviour, including online hate and bullying. Reporting over the phone is open Monday to Friday 8am - 8pm. The online reporting tool can be used at any time.
- Revenge Porn Helpline:** 0345 6000 459 or by email [here](#). Support if an intimate image of you is shared online, or if someone is threatening to do so. The helpline is open: Monday to Friday from 10 am - 4pm.
- National Stalking Helpline:** 0808 802 0300 or by email [here](#). Support if you are a victim of stalking and obsessive behaviour. The helpline is open: Monday and Wednesday 9.30am - 8pm; Tuesday, Thursday, Friday 9.30am - 4pm. (BSL available)
- Safer Places:** 03301 025811. Support for people suffering domestic abuse, including advice for accommodation and outreach. The helpline is open 24 hours a day and can guide you to support in your local area.

Emergency banner: In an emergency call 999. Navigation: Home, Resources, About, Feedback. Search bar with 'Submit' button. Quick Exit button in the bottom right corner.

Figure 4 I need help now! page

The list presented here is not exhaustive, but was suggested to us by workshop collaborators, and gives a cross-section of different helplines. Future iterations could include more of a cross-section, for example Southall Black Sisters offers support for Black and minoritized women suffering from GBV. One issue raised by workshop collaborators, and enacted here, was the need for information on the opening times, accessibility (e.g. British Sign Language), and different forms of contact available (e.g. chat, telephone number, email), in case circumstances would make it difficult to talk on the phone. It was also suggested that the information presented on this page should be brief, but give enough information for people to decide which service was most appropriate to them. If made public, there would be a need to continually monitor the accuracy of external links and front-line service availability hours.

Not visible in the image above, the bottom of the page also includes the text “If you see any helpline or support service missing, please use the feedback tab at the top of the page to make a suggestion”, which is hyperlinked to the Feedback page. Once made live, this would allow other services and users who had had a positive experience with a service to make recommendations for inclusion on the “I need help now!” page. Such a use of the toolkit would need someone available to moderate and manage suggestions to ensure resource additions are vetted to be safe, relevant, and useful.

I want to learn more

While the safety of users in an emergency was a priority in designing the visual organisation of the landing page, the core use and gap filled by the toolkit is accessible through the “I want to learn more” button. This opens up a resource library of filterable content (fig.5) that reflects the breadth of the challenge of TFGBV, and allows users to navigate to the most relevant information for them. As an education and information resource, the toolkit directs users to other information available online, tailored to their needs, through multiple selection. They also have the option to access the entire library in order to browse all content.

The filters are categorised in relation to a) the kind of user, b) the form of abuse, c) the kinds of technology involved in the abuse, and d) the type of resource needed. Clicking in the search box opens up the full list, or users can type into the box to bring up a specific term. Allowing all the terms to be viewable could again be triggering, but making the list visible also means that users might find a term that relates to what they are looking for but had not heard of yet. It might be the case, for instance, that a user is experiencing abuse but cannot

describe it; making the forms of abuse visible in the drop down menu possible for them to recognise and select what they may be facing. We have endeavoured to balance protecting the user whilst providing resources in a landscape in which terms are constantly changing.

Figure 5 Resource page - filter tool

Users can also add multiple words to a single search box, which reflects the way some terms are likely to co-occur in results or include umbrella terms and specific terms (e.g. image based abuse, sexting, intimate images, dick pics). This has the additional benefit that users can search for content where TFGBV may include many forms of abuse and technology, and users might be seeking multiple forms of information. A full list of the search terms is available in Appendix 1, and below are images of the search boxes' drop down feature (fig.6).

Figure 6 Dropdown menus expanded

The selection of terms can be as many or as few as the user wishes; the more filters selected, the more specific the search will be, whereas fewer terms will bring up more results. An empty search brings up the full resource list (a total of 60 resources, although many more

could be added to the library). Following the filtering of terms, the user can press submit to draw up the resources.

On the results page, a pop up button informs the user that the website will open a new tab in their browser that takes them to an external website (fig.7). This was a firm ask of our workshop collaborators, and part of the practice of building consent and safety-by-design into the toolkit. In line with the practices of consent, the pop up reappears to offer the user multiple points of for them to navigate through or away from the site. We made a conscious decision that this should be bright and clear, with a larger font size to emphasise its importance. An additional piece of text here could indicate that the external website has not been produced by the toolkit owners, and thus while it has been vetted as being reliable, its content has been created by another organisation.

After clicking on the link to continue, the user can see the full results of the search in a gallery view (fig.8). Each gallery page includes 12 tiles (with multiple pages if the results list is higher), and each tile in the gallery is hyperlinked out to the resource. The tiles also include a short summary of the content contained within the resource, allowing the user to decide if each resource will be relevant for them. We have embedded a tool that allows users to forward the link to the resource on to someone else via email, or to email it to themselves if they want to save the information or read at a later date.

Figure 7 Left: large-scale version of pop up button. Right: pop up button in context

Figure 8 Search results, image shows the full library/no keywords selected

We selected to include the logos in each of the tiles for two reasons. First, it means that users will have more of a sense of where the information is coming from. For example, in the above results (Fig.8), we might expect the information provided directly by OnlyFans to be different in tone and content to that provided about OnlyFans by SafetyDetectives. Second, we used the logos as a form of citation, crediting where the information was from, and to signal to the user that the information provided in each of the links had not been produced by the toolkit’s authors. This was important to us, especially in the case of legal and accredited services (e.g. health, counselling), where we are not qualified to offer such information or support. The logo indicates to the user that this is a collation of resources, not a source of information in its own right - even while that collation is partial and situated in our own knowledge base and that of our partner/stakeholders.

In recognition of the fact that we might be missing important resources, the bottom of the page also asks “Something missing? Know a missing resource that you think should be listed? Please let us know”, with a link to the Feedback page.

Feedback page

The feedback page is signposted at several points in the toolkit, to allow people to send links and resources, information, or recommendations for the site owners to consider including (fig.9). In the future, we would envisage this being used to crowdsource a much larger database of resources, assuming the toolkit has dedicated and fully funded moderators to ensure content is legitimate, relevant, and attendant to issues of equality, diversity, and inclusion. As suggested by workshop collaborators, this is labelled as “Feedback” - a change from an earlier “Contact Us” - to help indicate that the toolkit is not a service. We have added a note to the bottom of the Feedback page to further reinforce this.

The screenshot shows the Feedback page layout. At the top left is a logo of two hands holding a heart. Next to it is a search bar with the text "Search ..." and a "Submit" button. On the top right, there is a phone icon and the text "In an emergency call 999". Below this is a navigation menu with links for "Home", "Resources", "About", and "Feedback" (which is underlined). The main content area is split into two columns. The left column has the heading "Resources and recommendations" and the text "Do you have any feedback or know of any missing resources that you think should be listed?". The right column has a text input field labeled "Link to resource" and a "Send" button below it. At the bottom of the page, there is a note: "**Note - this website is not a monitored service, but there are many great organisations listed and referenced that offer individual advice, support, and professional guidance. If you need help right away, please click 'I need help now!'. If you are in an emergency, ring 999." Below the note is a small logo and the text "This website is designed to create a safer online and digital environment by guiding people directly to the helplines, support, guidance, and advice that they need." At the very bottom, there is a footer with "© 2024 All Rights Reserved." and a "Quick Exit" button with an external link icon.

Figure 9 Feedback page

To further prevent users looking for direct support from the toolkit owners, a future development could be an automatic reply to anything sent via the feedback tool letting people know how long it might take to respond or act on any feedback, and once more linking to the “I need help now!” page and to 999 in case of an emergency.

About page

The final page that we want to share in this report is the About page (fig.10). This page gives information on the project itself, a brief overview of what the toolkit aims to achieve, and information on the project funder. Most importantly, it recognises the contributions made by our workshop collaborators in compiling this toolkit, and their knowledge and expertise in guiding us to the urgent need for such a resource in the sector and in tackling TFGBV.

Figure 10 About page

Conclusions

TFGBV is deeply connected to and embedded in the wider endemic of violence against women and girls, and is therefore part of a national emergency (National Police Chiefs' Council, 2024). However, despite a range of excellent resources existing online to educate, inform, advise, and support, there is currently no space that collates and produces a database of these resources. Such a database would be as useful for a victim-survivor as it would be helping a practitioner in guiding a patient/client to the best services for their situation, and thus the best care or information on seeking justice. There is also a broader educational piece addressed in this project; of sharing information so that people can become more informed about the types of TFGBV and what their implications are for all of us, as well as raising awareness around the breadth of what constitutes technology-facilitated abuse. In this report, we have set out the context in which a toolkit bringing together a number of resources - one that can be filtered to address specific forms of technology, abuse, and audience - is necessary, as well as offered a prototype of what such a toolkit could look like, how it could work, and what its affordances should be to triage information effectively and safely.

The toolkit we have described above has been built drawing on workshops with a number of expert collaborators. Some of the key outcomes of these discussions has included the following:

1. The challenge of TFGBV, when so much is changing in regulatory and legal frameworks, set against the complete normalisation of some forms of TFGBV in our cultural environment, and the advances in technology that generate a constant cycle of new forms of abuse. This creates a need for an up-to-date and constantly revised database of relevant material;
2. The need for a safety-by-design approach that puts the potential victim-survivor at the centre of the design of any toolkit, while recognising other relevant audiences, include the educational value and fast-paced change in forms of TFGBV and their associated terminologies;

3. The need for continuing cross-sector working, including the publicisation of the wide range of resources out there (as well as identification of spaces where support is missing or under resourced), so that referral for someone dealing with TFGBV is targeted and specific, and gaps in support can be addressed.

The toolkit that we have co-designed with our workshop collaborators is a practical option to meet some of these needs. While it provides valuable resources for users seeking information on abuse that has occurred, or continues to occur, it is necessary to also address the challenge from a preventative standpoint. As such, our current and ongoing project, “Preventing digital gender-based violence in the UK and Spain: Cross-cultural collaboration through widening education and literacy” is working with academic and charity partners in Spain and the UK to co-produce a scalable model for prevention work across the global challenge and threat of TFGBV, to work alongside the toolkit described here. Specifically, we are building an adaptable and multilingual strategic framework for TFGBV intervention to be prototyped in the Spanish and UK contexts, and with the capacity to be scaled further, that provides 1) a commitment to targeting TFGBV at the government and policy level; 2) a ‘mapping’ of impact actor networks across the UK and Spain for future collaboration; and 3) “future proofing” for emergent trends around digital violence including the use of AI and remote location tracking.

In addition to this ongoing research, two further issues that highlighted in the discussions generated from this project, ones that should be incorporated into the future direction of research in this area. These were: the protection of children and young people, and; the need to educate boys and men on TFGBV. These two issues are outside the remit of this project. Where we have approached this work with a broad definition of TFGBV, we are conscious of the different skills and expertise needed for these two publics. We wish to recognise them here as important areas for further development, with specific tools and approaches needed to reach these audiences.

The prototype that we have built is fully functioning and viable, and this report has documented both how it works and what further developments would be needed, including the requirement for dedicated and expert maintenance and moderation of any live version of the toolkit. As set out in this report, there is an urgency to seeing such a platform becoming accessible to the public, and to the audiences identified as potential users, in the future:

either through further development of the current existing resource library, or in it acting as inspiration to other organisations with a vested interest in addressing VAWG and its relationship with technology in our heavily digitally mediated worlds. Through wider accessibility, we would argue, such a toolkit would become a valuable resource and tool for change in tackling existing and developing forms violence and their wider impact on our society, health, wellbeing, and relationships.

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Appendix 1: Toolkit categories

I need help for:	Dealing with abuse:	Technology help:	Resource needed:
Friend or family	Abuse	Adult content sites	Advice
Law enforcement	Abusive relationships	AI	Assessment
Myself	Assault	Airpods	Blocking
Patient or client	Blackmail	Airtags	Courses
Researcher	Catfishing	Apple watch	FAQ
Student	Coercion	Banking	Guide
Users	Coercive behaviour	Chat sites	Helpline
	Control	Computer/tablet	Information/education
	Cyberattack	Contraception	Legal
	Cyberbullying	Cycle tracker	News
	Cybercrime	Dating apps	Policy
	Cyberflashing	Digital app	Reporting
	Data privacy	Doorbell camera	Research
	Deep fake	Find my phone	Resources
	Dick pics	FitBit	Safety
	Domestic abuse	Gaming console	Support
	Downblousing	Image sharing	Tool
	Economic abuse	Meta	Training
	Emotional abuse	Only Fans	Video
	Extortion	Phone	
	Fake profiles	Smart home	
	Financial coercion	Social media	
	Grooming	Streaming	
	Hacking	Video	
	Harassment	Video camera	
	Hatespeech	Virtual assistants	
	Image based abuse	VR	
	Image manipulation	Wearables	
	Information sharing	Webcam	
	Intimate images	Websites	
		YouTube	

	Intimate partner abuse Intimidation Location sharing Manipulation Misogyny Non-consensual Password security Privacy Revenge porn Safety Scam Self-harm Sexting Sexual harassment Stalking Surveillance Threat to share Threatening behaviour Tracking Trafficking Unwanted attention Upskirting Violence Voice manipulation Voyeurism		
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